

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF VITAMIN D SUPPLEMENTATION ON
GLUCOSE METABOLISM IN POLYCYSTIC OVARY
SYNDROME**¹Dr Atika Batool, ¹Dr Isra Jamil, ¹Dr Naila Amjad
¹House Officer at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad

Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

Introduction: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrinopathy in women of reproductive age, with a prevalence up to 10% depending on which diagnostic criteria are used.

Objectives of the study: The basic objective of the study is to analyse the vitamin D supplementation on glucose metabolism in polycystic ovary syndrome.

Methodology of the study: This cross sectional study was conducted in Allied Hospital, Faisalabad during July 2018 to January 2019. The data was collected from 100 female patients who were suffering from PCOS and visited the OPD of the hospital regularly. Regarding the cardiovascular profile, information was collected on BMI and systolic and diastolic blood pressure in both PCOS and comparison women.

Results: The data was collected from 100 individuals. There was no significant correlation ($P = 0.09$) between values for 25-OHD and 25-(OH)₂D. Ten per cent of the women ($n = 50$) had serum 25-OHD levels below 12 ng mL. This subgroup also had significantly lower serum 25-(OH)₂D (24.9 vs. 27.9 pg mL, $P = 0.05$), but they did not differ from the rest with regard to PTH and P-calcium levels.

Conclusion: It is concluded that there is a significant association between vitamin D status and metabolic disturbances in patients with PCOS. Moreover, PCOS women had a significant lower serum 25(OH)D compared to fertile controls.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Atika Batool,**

House Officer at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Atika Batool et al., *Analysis of Vitamin D Supplementation on Glucose Metabolism in Polycystic Ovary Syndrome.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrinopathy in women of reproductive age, with a prevalence up to 10% depending on which diagnostic criteria are used. It is characterized by ovulatory dysfunction, hyperandrogenism and/or polycystic ovarian morphology [1]. Metabolic disturbances are present in a majority of the women suffering from PCOS, i.e. 30–40% have impaired glucose tolerance and insulin resistance with compensatory hyperinsulinemia, and as many as 10% will develop type 2 diabetes mellitus during their fourth decade [2].

Adipose tissue dysfunction has been implicated as a contributor to insulin resistance in women with PCOS. However, a substantial number of lean women affected by PCOS have insulin resistance as well, independent of obesity. Vitamin D deficiency has been proposed as the possible missing link between insulin resistance and PCOS. Vitamin D is a fat-soluble vitamin that is synthesized endogenously through sunlight-induced photochemical conversion of cholesterol to 7-dehydrocholesterol in the skin or obtained from the diet [3].

Subsequently vitamin D undergoes a hydroxylation twice, first vitamin D is transported to the liver where it is rapidly hydroxylated by 25-hydroxylase into 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH)D). The second hydroxylation occurs in the kidney and is catalyzed by 1 alpha-hydroxylase to form 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25(OH)₂D), the active metabolite of vitamin D. Circulating 1,25(OH)₂D binds to vitamin D receptors (VDR) to initiate its effect. Serum 25(OH)D is the major circulating form of vitamin D and is used as the main indicator of vitamin D status. Its half-life is 2–3 weeks compared to only 4–6 hours for 1, 25(OH)₂D [4]. Since many years, a role for vitamin D has been suggested outside the calcium and bone homeostasis,

due to the identification of the VDR, and the enzyme 1 alpha-hydroxylase in many more tissues, including the pancreatic beta-cells, immune cells and reproductive organs in both genders [5]. Moreover, this assumption is supported by the finding that the active vitamin D-vitamin D receptor complex regulates over 300 genes, including genes that are important for glucose and lipid metabolism as well gonadal function [6].

Objectives of the study:

The basic objective of the study is to analyse the vitamin D supplementation on glucose metabolism in polycystic ovary syndrome.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Allied Hospital, Faisalabad during July 2018 to January 2019. The data was collected from 100 female patients who were suffering from PCOS and visited the OPD of the hospital regularly. Regarding the cardiovascular profile, information was collected on BMI and systolic and diastolic blood pressure in both PCOS and comparison women. In PCOS women, waist circumference, fasting glucose, insulin and lipid profile (i.e. total cholesterol, triglycerides, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol) were additionally measured. The data was collected and analysed using SPSS version 18.0.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 individuals. There was no significant correlation ($P = 0.09$) between values for 25-OHD and 25-(OH)₂D. Ten per cent of the women ($n = 50$) had serum 25-OHD levels below 12 ng mL. This subgroup also had significantly lower serum 25-(OH)₂D (24.9 vs. 27.9 pg mL, $P, 0.05$), but they did not differ from the rest with regard to PTH and P-calcium levels.

Table 01: Analysis of socio-demographic values of PCOS patients

	PCOS	Control	p-value
Age (y)	34 ± 5	32 ± 5	< 0.01
Body Mass Index (kg/m ²)	25.2 (22.0–30.4)	24.0 (22.0–27.0)	< 0.01
Ethnicity (%)			
Caucasian	385 (60)	382 (85)	< 0.01
Non-Caucasian	254 (40)	67 (15)	

BP systolic (mmHg)	118 ± 13	114 ± 11	< 0.01
BP diastolic (mmHg)	77 ± 11	73 ± 9	< 0.01
Serum 25(OH)D (nmol/l)	49.0 (27.1–74.1)	64.5 (39.2–85.7)	< 0.01
Storage of samples (years)	6	10	< 0.01

25(OH)D, 25-hydroxy vitamin D; BP, blood pressure.

Table 02: Serum Vit-D and lipid profile of patients

	PCOS	
	B (95% CI)	p
TC (mmol/L)	0.16 (-0.13–0.46)	0.27
TG (mmol/L)	-0.28 (-0.44 —0.12)	< 0.01
HDL (mmol/L)	0.34 (0.23–0.45)	< 0.01
LDL (mmol/L)	0.05 (-0.20–0.29)	0.70
TC/HDL ratio (mmol/L)	-0.79 (-1.12 —0.46)	< 0.01
Apo A1 (g/L)	23.1 (9.2–37.0)	< 0.01
Apo B (g/L)	-9.8 (-18.9 —0.8)	0.03

DISCUSSION:

Melhus et al conducted study, plasma 25-hydroxyvitamin-D level and fracture risk in a community-based cohort of elderly men in Sweden on 1194 person and found 309 of the participants (26%) sustained a fracture [7]. 25 (OH) D levels below 40 nmol/liter, which corresponded to the fifth percentile of 25 (OH) D, were associated with a modestly increased risk for fracture. No risk difference was detected above this level [8]. Approximately 3% of the fractures were attributable to low 25 (OH) D levels in this population.

Vitamin D is thought to influence the development of PCOS through gene transcription and influences metabolism. The effect of vitamin D status on glucose metabolism appears to be mediated by direct and indirect pathways. A direct effect on insulin secretion may be mediated by activation of VDRs in the pancreatic beta-cell with the addition of the presence of 1 α -hydroxylase to locally produce 1,25(OH)₂D. Furthermore, the direct effect of vitamin D on insulin secretion is supported by the presence of the vitamin D-response element in the human insulin promoter

gene [9]. Vitamin D deficiency may also increase systemic inflammation, known to play an important role in the pathogenesis of insulin resistance. Finally, insulin secretion and insulin resistance are both calcium-dependent processes. Both could be influenced by vitamin D status through an alteration in calcium concentration and flux through cell membranes of pancreas and insulin-responsive tissues [10]. Another study from India on healthy individuals also reported similar results. However, this is contradictory to the findings from the same population of South Asian women living in the United Kingdom where serum 25(OH)D deficiency was associated with a progressive reduction in bone mass [11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that there is a significant association between vitamin D status and metabolic disturbances in patients with PCOS. Moreover, PCOS women had a significant lower serum 25(OH)D compared to fertile controls.

REFERENCES:

1. Van der Mei IA, Ponsonby AL, Engelsen O, Pasco JA, McGrath JJ, Eyles DW et al. The high prevalence of vitamin D insufficiency across Australian populations is only partly explained by season and latitude. *Environ Health Perspect* 2007; 115: 1132-9.
2. Lips P. Worldwide status of vitamin D nutrition. *J steroid Biochem Mol Biol*. 2010; 121: 297-300.
3. Alfaham M, Woodhead S, Pask G, Davies D. Vitamin D deficiency: a concern in pregnant Asian women. *Br J Nutr* 1995; 73: 881-7.
4. Boucher BJ, Mannan N and Cunningham J. Vitamin D status and bone mass in UK South Asian women. *Bone*. 2007; 40: 1182; author reply 3. (Check for this specific reply no. Could not find it)
5. Fahim F. The magnitude of low bone mineral [corrected] density in middle and old age women. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2005; 55: 500-2.
6. Song Y, Wang L, Pittas AG, Del Gobbo LC, Zhang C, Manson JE et al. Blood 25-hydroxy vitamin D levels and incident type 2 diabetes: a meta-analysis of prospective studies. *Diabetes Care* 2013. 36 1422–1428.
7. Joergensen C, Gall MA, Schmedes A, Tarnow L, Parving HH, Rossing P. Vitamin D levels and mortality in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2010. 33 2238–2243.
8. Ferder M, Inserra F, Manucha W, Ferder L. The world pandemic of vitamin D deficiency could possibly be explained by cellular inflammatory response activity induced by the renin-angiotensin system. *American Journal of Physiology: Cell Physiology* 2013. 304 C1027–C1039.
9. Sugden JA, Davies JI, Witham MD, Morris AD, Struthers AD. Vitamin D improves endothelial function in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and low vitamin D levels. *Diabetic Medicine* 2008. 25320–325.
10. Vimalaswaran KS, Cavadino A, Berry DJ, Jorde R, Dieffenbach AK, Lu C et al. Association of vitamin D status with arterial blood pressure and hypertension risk: a mendelian randomisation study. *Lancet Diabetes and Endocrinology* 2014. 2 719–729.
11. Chagas CE, Borges MC, Martini LA, Rogero MM. Focus on vitamin D, inflammation and type 2 diabetes. *Nutrients* 2012. 4 52–67.